

Training report for pix2pix model (pix2pix-tom20-11122023)

Date: 2023-12-12

Training time: 5.0hour(s) 20.0min(s) 19sec(s)

Information for your materials and method:

The pix2pix model was trained from scratch for 200 epochs on 2944 paired image patches (image dimensions: (512, 512), patch size: (512,512)) with a batch size of 3 and a vanilla GAN loss function, using the pix2pix ZeroCostDL4Mic notebook (v 1) (von Chamier & Laine et al., 2021). Key python packages used include tensorflow (v 2.12.0), numpy (v 1.22.4), torch (v 2.0.1), cuda (v 11.5.119

Build cuda_11.5.r11.5/compiler.30672275_0). The training was accelerated using a GPU.

Augmentation: The dataset was augmented by a factor of 2 by

- rotation
- flipping
- random zoom magnification

Parameters

The following parameters were used for training:

Parameter	Value
number_of_epochs	200
patch_size	512x512
batch_size	3
initial_learning_rate	0.0005

Training Dataset

Training_source: /home/pix2pix-tom20-11122023/Training_source_norm

Training_target: /home/pix2pix-tom20-11122023/Training_target_norm

Model Path: /home/results/pix2pix-tom20-11122023

Example Training pair

Training source

Training target

References:

- ZeroCostDL4Mic: von Chamier, Lucas & Laine, Romain, et al. "Democratising deep learning for microscopy with ZeroCostDL4Mic." Nature Communications (2021).
- pix2pix: Isola, Phillip, et al. "Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks." Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. 2017.
- Augmentor: Bloice, Marcus D., Christof Stocker, and Andreas Holzinger. "Augmentor: an image augmentation library for machine learning." arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.04680 (2017).

Important:

Remember to perform the quality control step on all newly trained models

Please consider depositing your training dataset on Zenodo